

EFFICACY OF SNUHI SIDDHA TRIPHALA IN VICHARCHIKA

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Article Received on 26 Sept. 2025,
Article Revised on 17 Oct. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434212>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Deodatta Bhadlikar, Dr. Devyani Bhadlikar, Dr. Shruti Saxena*³, Dr. Archana Pandey Jumle, Rahul Jumle. (2025). EFFICACY OF SNUHI SIDDHA TRIPHALA IN VICHARCHIKA. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(20), 1056-1059.

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INTRODUCTION

Many drugs are prescribed for 'Shodhana' in ancient medical science of india, (Ayurveda) and amongst them several drugs are in running practice of Vaidyas since long.

Madanphala, Vacha, Nimba, Devadali are prescribed for Vaman Trivrut, Jayapala, Argvadha, Haritaki, Triphala, Aswakanchuki, ichhabhedi, Naracha Rasa, are prescribed for Virechana which are commonly in practice of Vaidyas.

During pilot study for Vamana Virechana appropriate Shodhana was not observed with the use of above stated drugs. Hinayoga of the above Karmas are observed with the use of some drugs and side effects like burning in throat, chest or stomach are observed with the use of the same drugs and that has become troublesome to the patients to use.

After considerable thinking and discussion Snuhi-Kshira and Triphala were tried. The bulk of fresh Snuhikshira is collected and the drug was prepared for our trial.

WHAT IS SNUHI BHAVIT TRIPHALA

Snuhi Bhavit Triphala is prepared with fresh Snuhi Kshira and Triphala (Sambhaga Triphala) Churna was given one Bhavana of Snuhi Kshira in stone mortars for one day. Then it was kept in open shadow to dry it for a period of a day and the dry powder was preserved in glass bottle.

METHOD AND MATERIALS

The trial of Snuhi Bhavit Triphala was conducted. Before the trial is carried out patients were kept on places for a period of three days. Under observation time modern investigations were carried out like urine R and M; stool routine, and Microscopic and Hemogram.

SNEHANA

After three days observation 'Snehana' is started with Panchatikta-Ghruta in increased dose of 20 grams daily upto 140 grams for 7 days. During the process of Snehana patients were kept on milk diet and were restricted to use cold water open air etc.

Generally Samyag Yoga of Snehana is observed within 7 days. After reaching that stage one day gap was kept before Vamana and three days gap before Virechana, according to classics.

VAMAN KARMA

If a patient is fit for Vamana after keeping one day gap, on previous evening patient was given Utkarica prepared with Masha and Rice with curd in diet and the next early morning patient were given 3 liters milk and then the dose of one gram Snuhi Bhavit Triphala with cold water, administered. Each stage of Vamanavega along with blood Pressure, pulse etc. were closely observed and noted.

VIRECHANA

If a patient is selected for Virechana after keeping three days gap with continuation of milk diet were given 2 grams of Snuhi Bhavit Triphala according to his 'Kostha' on the fourth day early morning with cold water, Each Vega was observed and blood pressure pulse etc. were noted.

OBSERVATION

Total 42 cases were studied. Out of them 23 cases were male and 19 patients were female. (See table)

Classification of age group is shown under

1 to 10 years old 6 patients were treated,

11 to 20 years old 4 patients were treated,

21 to 30 years old 12 patients were treated,

31 to 40 years old 10 patients were treated,

41 to 50 years old 10 patients were treated,

We found more number of patients between the age group of 21 to 40 years, Looking to the Tridosha Theory the stage of Pitta Vruddhi Kala as middle age.

Vicharchika is a Pitta Pradhan disease and Virechana is a suitable treatment for Pitta.

DETAILS OF CRONICITYS

6 Patients were treated of 1 month duration,

6 Patients were treated of 3 month duration,

8 Patients were treated of 6 month duration.

6 Patients were treated of 12 month duration.

12 Patients were treated of 2 years duration.

4 Patients were treated of 2 years duration

Looking to the above details maximum number of 12 patients were found of 2 years duration and that includes of Kasthasadhya State. The above trial was carried out by Vamana in 7 Patients and Virechana in 35 Patients.

An effect of Vaman and Virechan in these cases of Vicharchika is classified in groups according to the result.

(1) Prashama (Cure) (2) Laxanalpata Relief in some symptoms) (1) Alabha No Cure)

The above classification is subjective of relief in signs and symptoms of more than 10% is 'Prashama', relief up to 50% is a (Laxanalpata) and relief below 25% is 'Alabha'.

With the trial of Snuhi Bhavit Triphala, Prasama was observed in 20 cases (i.e. 47.6%) Laxanalpata is observed in 12 cases (i.e. 28.5%) and Alabha is observed in 10 cases (i.e. 23.81%) with the trial of Snuhi Shavit Triphala.

DISCUSSION

Charaka has described that "Kushtha Roga" is a "Deergh Roganam Shrestha' means "Kushtha Roga" is a more difficult to cure in Chronic diseases.

Snuhi Bhavit Triphala is found very effective for Vamana and Virechana Karma without any side effect and Toxic effect. In the cases of Vicharchika. 47.62% cure is observed with only Shodhan treatment without giving any Shamana treatment, 28.57% showed improvement in more than 30% complaints and 23.81% showed no improvement.

Vicharchika is a Pitta-Pradhan Tridosha Kshudra Kushtha, The etiological factors provoke Doshas at gastrointestinal level then due to derangement of digestion the vitiated dosha enters the circulation and tissue level also. The vitiation created at Dhatu level to occur Vicharchika causes. Removal of Vitiated doshas is the treatment of Ayurveda. And some specific method to remove the Vitiated Doshas is prescribed in texts. According to that method for' the purpose of Snehan, Pancha Tikta Ghrut in increasing dose 20 grams to 140 grams daily for 7 days given to the patients by that level of serum cholesteral is increased and fat soluble vitiated Doshas dissolve and absorb in the blood stream and thrown in elementary canal then by the Shodhan Karma the Vitiated Doshas are thrown out from the body and the disease Vicharchika is relieved.

SUMMARY

In the treatment of Vicharchika, the elemination by Vamana and Virechana is the treatment of choice. The effect of Snuhi Bhavit Triphala is effectove and Virecnana in this disorder.